

TEACHING COMPETENCIES AND THEIR ROLE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SOME SKILLFUL QUALITIES OF YOUNG CHILDREN

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Abstract:

This study aimed to investigate the use of teaching competences and its role on the development of basic motor skills of primary school children (from 6 to 7 years old). The sample population consisted of 40 pupils (girls and boys), the researcher have found that: (1), the formation of goals within teaching by competences units in the form of skills are easy to be identified and distinguished with the use of a level of acceptance for the performance (efficiency indicators) and (2), the impact of teaching by competences units through different performances of the skills, the static kinetic conditions and dynamic ones in the improvement of the capacity to held up the constancy of the body, and the capacity to overcome the impact of gravitational forces for the experimental sample.

Keywords: teaching competencies; some skillful qualities; young children

1. Introduction

This study tend to clarify the new concept of teaching by competences and its effect on the development of the child's basic motor skills which expresses the progressive

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aspects in physical education and sport pedagogy during primary education through, first the reliance on basic movement abilities according to (Oussama Kamel Ratib, et al, 1982) and second through using the latest theories of teaching which is teaching by competences depending on the idea of locomotors exploration, where the child learns how and why he moves.

Previous studies that have dealt with this topic were not sufficient, that's why the researcher choose to deal with this research: to shed light on the development of a child's basic motor skills by using teaching by competences technique before school by creating good conditions so that the child find it easy to try and show his movements. However, the teacher should be aware of the way he acts with the child where he shouldn't act as a dictator but he should help the child rely on his imagination to show off their both innate and acquired abilities.

The reason why the researcher tries to deal with this topic is: first, it is original. Second, to show the amount of its scientific contribution in the construction of knowledge. In light of what is mentioned above, the researcher claimed the following question: *"does teaching by competences has an effect in the development of some basic skills for primary school children (from 6 to 7 years old)?"*

2. Material and Methods

2.1 The sample population

The selected population includes 40 pupils (girls and boys), from Khira Ould Houssin primary school, who are being selected randomly, their ages get between 6 to 7 years old, the researchers have distributed a sample for an exploratory experience as follows:

- Experimental sample: it includes 20 children (boys and girls).
- Control sample: it includes 20 children (boys and girls).
- Exploratory experiment sample: it includes 10 children (boys and girls).

2.2 Specifications of the used tests

- Running test 20 M: its purpose is to measure the running speed.
- Long jump test of fortitude: its purpose is to measure the strength of the leg's muscles of the child.
- Flinging test of fortitude its purpose is: measure the child's capacity to throw.
- Long jump running its purpose is: to measure the capacity to combine between running and jumping.
- Balance test: its purpose is to measure the child's capacity to control his body.

Table 1: Some of the applied tests

Honesty coefficient	Reability coefficient	Tabular value	Level of significance	Degree of freedom	The sample's size	Statistical studies tests
0.99	0,99	0.38	0.05	09	10	Running test 20M
0.97	0,96					Long jump test of fortitude
0.98	0,98					Flinging test of fortitude
0.98	0,98					Long jump running
0,91	0,83					Dynamic equilibrium
0,91	0,83					Static equilibrium

In order to develop the basic motor skills, the researchers suggested a series of kinetic exercises within the educational units that are based on teaching by competences, where 28 units have been used, two units were used for pre and post tests, rate of two units per week while the experimental research samples have used the educational units that are based on teaching by competences and for the control group it relied on the normal program.

The researchers have suggested a series of teaching by competences units in order to develop the basic motor skills of primary school children through the use of different teaching methods.

Table 2: The time-volume and percentage for a single session

Percentage (%)		Time (minutes)		Stages	
25	3	12.5	1.5	Administrative Part	Preparatory
	22		11	Warm Up Part	
65		32.5		Main	
10		5		Final	

Table 3: The time-volume and percentage for 24 sessions

Percentage (%)		Time (minutes)		Stages	
25	3	250	36	Administrative Part	
	22		300	Warm Up Part	
65		780		Main	
10		120		Final	

Table 4: The results of both the pre and post tests for control and experimental samples

Statistical significance	Level of significance	Degree of freedom	sample	t tabular	t calculated	Post test		Pre-test		Research samples	tests
						s	$\bar{x}$	s	$\bar{x}$		
ddl	0.05	19	20	1.72	3.06	s	$\bar{x}$	s	$\bar{x}$	experimental	running 20 m
ddl						0.57	4.10	0.46	4.92		
ddl					1.81	0.64	5.26	0.49	5.28	control	
ddl					4.73	0.25	1.21	0.23	1.19	experimental	Long jump of fortitude
ddl					3.70	0.18	1.12	0.17	1.11	control	
ddl					8.33	0.47	3.43	0.52	3.40	experimental	Flinging for fortitude
ddl					6.99	0.61	3.01	0.44	2.95	control	
ddl					5.62	0.29	1.55	0.30	1.53	experimental	Long jump running
ddl					2.58	0.37	1.39	0.32	1.38	control	
ddl					7.03	0.58	1.65	0.58	1.35	experimental	Dynamic equilibrium
ddl					4.87	0.57	1.30	0.61	1.20	control	
ddl					6.66	0.51	1.51	0.58	1.35	Experimental	Static equilibrium
ddl					4.87	0.48	1.15	0.51	1.05	control	

3. Conclusions

- Teaching by competences units had a positive effect on all the basic motor skills for the experimental sample through using multiple kinetic patterns to build up a certain competences in sequence and flow.
- The formation of goals within teaching by competences units in the form of skills that are easy to be identified and distinguished with the use of a level of acceptance for the performance (efficiency indicators) have a great influence in the development of the basic motor skills for the experimental sample.
- The impact of teaching by competences units through different performances of the skills and the static kinetic conditions and dynamic ones in the improvement of the capacity to held up the constancy of the body and the capacity to overcome the impact of gravitational forces for the experimental sample.
- The positive impact of using teaching by competences units for the experimental sample in the development of the eye- hand compatibility also in the manual dexterity that is reflected in throwing test.
- The good results that the experimental sample has gained attribute to the effect of teaching by competences units and reject the effect of growth or the normal program.
- Although the equivalence of the results of both the experimental sample and the control group, the attainment value was better for the experimental sample.

4. Recommendations

- The necessity to take care of pre-school children for being the most fertile stage of life for learning, building concepts, acquiring skills and enriching life experiences.
- Put an educational program that aims to achieve intellectual and physical development for pre-school children through the use of the latest teaching theories which is teaching by competences.
- The need to include programs for the development of the motor basic skills into the physical education and sport curricula for primary stage.
- When teaching by competence, there should be a focus on the formation of attitudes that evoke a child where it constitute a challenge for their abilities so that he/she develops their basic motor sources.
- Reliance on teaching by competences units that are presented by the researcher which encourage the development of the basic motor skills for this category.

- Condensation on researches and studies that deal with impact of physical education and sport programs on this category.

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